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Investigation of Novel Fire Retardant Polyfurfuryl Alcohol (PFA) Bio-Composite Material

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SHD and University of Derby

Jack Holyoak

Part Time Degree course (BEng Mechanical Engineering) completed at the University of Derby whilst working for SHD Composite Materials. Final year project on the 'Characterisation of Polyfurfuryl alcohol bioresin within advanced composites'.

Dr Tahir Sharif

Project supervisor and senior lecturer at the University of Derby. Responsible for the composites laboratory and PFA research at the University.

Dr Alix Sauget

Project supervisor and R&D Manager at SHD Composite Materials. Instrumental in the development of SHD's novel bio resin system and advancement of R&D test facilities.

SHD – Introduction

- Company: Founded in **2010** by **Steve** and **Helen Doughty**, supported by a highly experienced team.
- Manufacturing: Component & Tooling pre-impregnated materials or “**prepreg**”.
- Fibres / fabrics: All types (carbon, glass, aramid, natural...).
- Resins: Bespoke in house formulation.

UK
Headquarters, R&D
3 production lines

Slovenia
1 production line

US
1 production line

Carbon prepreg

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SHD – Research and Development

1. Formulation of resin systems

- Epoxy
- Bio-resins
- Specialist systems: OOA, Flame retardant, High service temperature, etc.

Typical epoxy polymer chain

2. Technical Support

- Highly experienced technical support team (materials & processing)
- Autoclave and oven curing capability
- Material characterisation and qualification support

3. Analysis of material properties

- DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimetry): Cure, Thermal
- DMA (Dynamic Mechanical Analysis): Cure, Thermal
- Rheometry: Cure, Viscosity
- Mechanical testing machine: Mechanical properties

Laboratory equipment

Introduction to PFA Resin Systems

Initial situation:

- SHD manufactured a small range of Hot Melt phenolic materials for certain applications requiring Flame, Smoke and Toxicity (FST) properties.
- Internal and customers HSE concerns: carcinogenic ingredients, REACH implications.
- A change was required for future-proofing.

Phenol - formaldehyde

GHS06 – Acute toxicity

GHS08 – Health hazard

Introduction to PFA Resin Systems

Answer:

1. PFA (*Polyfurfuryl Alcohol*) based resin systems introduced initially to maintain FST criteria whilst improving safety and sustainability.

- No hazardous substances: formaldehyde free, phenol free.
- No VOC's, curing only produces water.

Complete material characterisation performed to generate the data required by users.

PFA Resins – Sustainability, Health and Safety

- By-product of cane sugar production.
- Derived from waste stream – no dedicated land / resource usage.
- Secured supply chain – no fossil fuel derivation. Huge source material availability.

PFA Resins – Sustainability, Health and Safety

- Hot melt processed, no VOC's: safe to use on prepreg production lines and for end users.
- Increased bio-based content in composite materials:

	Resin bio-based content	Composite bio-based content (40%RW)	Composite bio-based content – natural fibres (40%RW)
Bisphenol A epoxy resin	Up to 30%	Up to 12%	Up to 62%
PFA bio-resin	94 - 98%	38 - 39%	98 - 99%

*Bisphenol A epoxy resin components
Epichlorhydrin can be bio-derived*

Glass & Carbon fibres PFA composites

Flax fibres PFA composite

PFA Characterisation

➤ Aero specifications: combination of heat released, toxic fumes & flame propagation tests

FR308 FST properties – Aircraft interiors standard: CS 25.853

<i>Test</i>	<i>Result</i>	<i>Limit</i>	
▪ Heat Release Peak (<i>kW/m²</i>)	20.4	65	PASS
▪ Heat Release Total (<i>kW.min/m²</i>)	14.2	65	PASS
▪ Smoke Density	4.3	200	PASS
▪ Toxic Gas Emission:			PASS
▪ 60s vertical burn (<i>in.</i>)	0.2	6	PASS
▪ 15s horizontal burn (<i>in./min</i>)	0.0	2.5	PASS

Performed on 8 plies laminates (FR308, 7781 glass, 33%RW)

Applications: galleys, seats, lockers, etc.

<i>Gas</i>	<i>Result</i>	<i>Limit</i>
• CO	115	1000
• HCN	1	150
• HF	0	100
• HCL	2	150
• SO ₂	0	100
• Nox	5	100

PFA Characterisation

Thermal properties

- Service temperature > 85°C after initial cure (typical ground survival temperature).
- Glass transition temperature (T_g) develops as exposure to temperature increases.
- Post cure recommended for higher service temperature applications.

1h @ 120°C initial cure: $T_g > 115^\circ\text{C}$

Post-cure

3h @ 150°C post-cure: $T_g > 175^\circ\text{C}$

PFA Characterisation

Mechanical properties

- Needs to perform as well as the phenolic material it is replacing.
 - Material: 8 ply laminates (PFA, 7781 glass, 38%RW)
 - Cure: 130°C, 6 bar pressure

Tested as per ISO 14125

Tested as per ISO 14125

Tested as per ISO 14130

- Results: Similar or better than phenolic reference materials cured under similar conditions.
 (A, B, C, D, E, F are figures for typical industrial phenolic products)

PFA Characterisation

Interlaminar Shear Strength Oven Vs Autoclave

- Autoclave – 6bar pressure
- Oven – Vac bag pressure only

8 ply laminates (PFA, 7781 glass, 38%RW)

Autoclave - 46% increase in ILSS

*Tested as per ISO 14130
Error bars = standard deviation*

PFA Characterisation

Flexural Properties Oven Vs Autoclave

- Autoclave – 6bar pressure
- Oven – Vac bag pressure only

8 ply laminates (PFA, 7781 glass, 38%RW)

Autoclave - 24% increase in Flexural Strength

*Tested as per ISO 14125
Error bars = standard deviation*

PFA Characterisation

Mechanical properties

Curing Challenges with Water

- Oven properties lower than autoclave: voids formed due to water vaporisation
- At 6 bar the boiling point of water is above typical curing temperatures – voids less likely to form from vaporisation. Autoclave 6 bar pressure reduces size/presence of voids.
- Introduction of intermediate dwell at 90°C improved oven cured laminate properties.

Panel Cross Sections
1. Oven Cured (void formation) 2. Autoclave Cured

Development continues...

➤ Comprehensive study of further cure cycle parameters

- Consumables
- Temperature
- Post-cure
- Etc...

➤ Effect on:

- Thermal properties
- Mechanical properties
- Material density
- Porosity
- Etc...

Laminate Construction: 8 (300 x 300mm) pies stacked 0° (inverting alternate pies)
 Fibre Density: 2.54
 Curing Ramp Rate: 2°C/min

Laminate Number	Cure Number	Vessel	Vented	Release	Cure Cycle				Outputs									
					Dwell 1		Dwell 2		Tg Onset (°C)	Tg Peak (°C)	Flex Strength (MPa)	Flex Modulus (GPa)	ILSS (MPa)	Laminate Density (g/cm³)	Laminate Thickness (mm)	Fibre Weight (g)	CPT (mm)	Fibre Volume Fraction (%)
					Time	Temp (°C)	Time	Temp (°C)										
L376	FYP-O_01	O	x	P**	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	120	190.2	240.2	484.2	21.8	30.2	1.67	2.12	306	0.285	45.06
L377	FYP-O_02	O	x	P**	00:30:00	90	01:30:00	120	190.2	256.4	528.2	21.8	30.2	1.68	2.10	306	0.288	45.89
L400	FYP-O_01	O	x	P	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	120	190.8	237.8	512.4	21.5	30.9	1.71	2.06	306	0.280	46.34
L401	FYP-O_02	O	x	P	00:30:00	90	01:30:00	120	196.9	255.2	532.4	21.8	30.0	1.71	2.06	306	0.280	46.34
L378	FYP-O_03	O	x	P	-	-	01:00:00	120	193.8	229.7	482.1	20.8	27.5	1.65	2.15	306	0.299	44.83
L379	FYP-O_04	O	x	P	-	-	01:30:00	120	195.2	258.9	534.6	20.5	30.0	1.52	2.35	306	0.294	41.01
L380	FYP-O_05	O	x	P	00:30:00	90	00:30:00	130	188.7	238.8	501.4	21.4	30.8	1.70	2.06	306	0.280	46.34
L381	FYP-O_06	O	x	P	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	130	195.0	249.2	528.4	21.4	30.1	1.70	2.07	306	0.289	46.96
L382	FYP-O_07	O	x	P	-	-	00:30:00	130	188.0	238.8	501.4	18.1	14.1	1.44	2.55	306	0.316	38.09
L383	FYP-O_08	O	x	P	-	-	01:00:00	130	195.4	261.9	521.4	16.5	14.2	1.42	2.56	306	0.313	38.55
L384	FYP-A_01	A	v	P	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	120	199.9	244.4	475.0	25.9	45.2	2.02	1.72	306	0.215	56.03
L385	FYP-A_02	A	v	P	00:30:00	90	01:30:00	120	192.9	253.9	443.6	23.8	43.5	2.03	1.73	306	0.216	55.71
L386	FYP-A_03	A	v	P	-	-	01:00:00	120	196.8	249.4	441.2	22.8	43.2	2.04	1.70	306	0.215	56.03
L387	FYP-A_04	A	v	P	-	-	01:30:00	120	198.9	256.6	427.6	24.0	42.1	2.02	1.76	306	0.220	54.76
L388	FYP-A_05	A	v	P	00:30:00	90	00:30:00	130	198.9	249.3	471.2	23.8	40.5	2.02	1.74	306	0.218	55.39
L389	FYP-A_06	A	v	P	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	130	195.9	261.5	466.7	23.9	39.0	2.02	1.73	306	0.216	55.71
L390	FYP-A_07	A	v	P	-	-	00:30:00	130	196.9	261.9	444.4	23.2	39.5	2.00	1.83	303	0.226	52.75
L391	FYP-A_08	A	v	P	-	-	01:00:00	130	196.9	261.9	495.1	23.8	42.4	1.99	1.93	306	0.224	53.94
L392	FYP-A_01	A	v	S	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	120	196.9	249.7	543.8	20.8	43.9	1.87	2.18	306	0.273	44.71
L393	FYP-A_02	A	v	S	00:30:00	90	01:30:00	120	196.9	257.2	544.4	19.7	43.3	1.89	2.16	306	0.270	44.62
L394	FYP-A_03	A	v	S	-	-	01:00:00	120	195.8	247.5	562.2	19.7	42.5	1.88	2.17	306	0.271	44.41
L395	FYP-A_04	A	v	S	-	-	01:30:00	120	199.9	254.2	559.9	19.8	39.7	1.87	2.26	306	0.275	43.81
L396	FYP-A_05	A	v	S	00:30:00	90	00:30:00	130	198.5	256.8	559.8	19.2	38.5	1.88	2.18	306	0.273	44.71
L397	FYP-A_06	A	v	S	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	130	192.6	256.2	569.5	19.8	36.2	1.88	2.16	306	0.270	44.62
L398	FYP-A_07	A	v	S	-	-	00:30:00	130	197.7	259.2	547.5	18.9	37.5	1.84	2.27	303	0.294	42.04
L399	FYP-A_08	A	v	S	-	-	01:00:00	130	197.7	259.2	544.9	20.2	39.0	1.87	2.18	306	0.273	44.71
L413	FYP-A_01-1	A	x	P	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	120	197.6	235.4	479.4	25.4	41.8	2.09	1.83	300	0.209	56.58
L414	FYP-A_01-1	A	x	P	00:30:00	90	01:30:00	120	195.5	241.2	493.7	24.2	34.0	2.00	1.96	300	0.210	56.34
L415	FYP-A_03-1	A	x	P	-	-	01:00:00	120	198.7	237.7	472.9	23.5	39.5	1.99	1.86	300	0.210	56.34
L416	FYP-A_04-1	A	x	P	-	-	01:30:00	120	197.9	238.1	472.0	23.0	38.0	1.95	1.90	300	0.206	57.27
L417	FYP-A_05-1	A	x	P	00:30:00	90	00:30:00	130	199.8	238.1	458.8	24.8	39.9	1.99	1.87	300	0.209	56.58
L418	FYP-A_06-1	A	x	P	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	130	198.9	237.8	481.1	18.1	38.1	1.73	2.21	306	0.221	54.85
L419	FYP-A_07-1	A	x	P	-	-	00:30:00	130	198.1	237.7	481.1	22.7	42.7	2.00	1.86	300	0.208	56.92
L420	FYP-A_08-1	A	x	P	-	-	01:00:00	130	199.9	237.7	481.1	21.8	41.8	1.99	1.76	300	0.213	55.58
L421	FYP-A_01-1	A	x	S	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	120	194.1	211.3	471.1	21.0	39.0	1.99	2.19	300	0.269	44.99
L422	FYP-A_02-1	A	x	S	00:30:00	90	01:30:00	120	197.1	230.8	472.8	20.8	38.6	2.00	2.01	300	0.261	45.21
L423	FYP-A_03-1	A	x	S	-	-	01:00:00	120	197.2	230.8	472.8	20.8	39.1	2.00	2.06	300	0.258	45.87
L424	FYP-A_04-1	A	x	S	-	-	01:30:00	120	195.9	218.7	472.0	21.0	37.4	1.94	2.09	300	0.261	45.21
L425	FYP-A_05-1	A	x	S	00:30:00	90	00:30:00	130	195.4	194.6	412.1	21.0	39.6	2.00	2.06	300	0.258	45.87
L426	FYP-A_06-1	A	x	S	00:30:00	90	01:00:00	130	194.8	200.2	388.6	18.8	34.7	1.88	2.17	306	0.271	44.81
L427	FYP-A_07-1	A	x	S	-	-	00:30:00	130	195.8	187.7	411.8	18.4	32.4	1.84	2.10	300	0.263	44.99
L428	FYP-A_08-1	A	x	S	-	-	01:00:00	130	196.6	187.9	398.9	18.7	30.5	1.87	2.05	300	0.256	46.09

Cure Process Key
 O = Oven Cured (Vacuum bag only)
 A = Autoclave Cured (8 bar)
 P = Perforated Release Film over laminate stack during cure
 S = Solid Release Film over laminate stack during cure